

A Sentiment Analysis Study of Banning Single-Use Plastic Bags Based on X Users' Attitude

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Abstract: Single-use plastics have become an urgent global environmental concern. The Indonesian government has attempted to introduce a policy that bans the use of single-use plastics as an initial step toward overcoming this issue. However, policy implementation often faces challenges from stakeholders. Therefore, this study aims to analyze public sentiment expressed on the X platform (formerly known as "Twitter") regarding the policy of banning single-use plastic bags in Indonesia. The methods used in this study include data collection, pre-processing (cleaning and transforming), labeling, modeling, and analysis using RapidMiner software. Tweet data were then analyzed using three machine learning methods, i.e., Naïve Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Decision Tree. Data were divided into training and test sets with a ratio of 60:40, 70:30, and 80:20. As many as 1038 refined datasets from 2019-2023 with related keywords were obtained. Based on the performance evaluation, the Naïve Bayes algorithm can improve its performance as the amount of training data increases, without overfitting. This algorithm achieves the highest accuracy of 89.73% at an 80:20 ratio. Furthermore, the classification results of the majority (70.6%) of the tweets showed positive support for the policy, 19.6% were negative, and 9.8% were neutral. In other words, the results of this sentiment classification can be used to monitor public responses and formulate environmentally friendly policies that are effective and supported by the majority.

Keywords: algorithm; machine learning; Naïve Bayes; sentiment; single-use plastic

1. Introduction

Single-use plastics are among the biggest environmental challenges facing the world¹⁻³. Items such as plastic bags, bottles, straws, food packaging, and disposable cutlery have become an integral part of everyday life (Figure 1). Wastes from single-use plastics are often disposed of as

solid waste, adding to the environmental burden and harming human health⁴⁻⁷. They not only generate waste that is difficult to decompose but also cause air pollution, global warming, ozone depletion, and climate change since their production still relies on massive fossil resources⁸⁻¹². Many countries worldwide are banning the use of single-use plastics¹³⁻¹⁶. Even in Indonesia, the problem of single-

use plastics has become a serious concern. The government introduced a policy of banning the use of single-use plastics as an initial step toward overcoming this environmental crisis^{17,18)}. Nevertheless, this action has certainly sparked various sentiments. Various parties often face challenges, so implementing this type of policy is not always easy¹⁹⁾.

Fig. 1: Examples of single-use plastics in daily life.

Analyzing public sentiment towards single-use plastic bans is useful in understanding public response and support. Sentiment data can be obtained from the X platform, formerly known as Twitter. It is one of the most active and diverse social media platforms and provides a rich source of data to analyze public views, feelings, and opinions regarding these issues²⁰⁾. The main goal of sentiment analysis is to identify an author's attitude toward a particular topic, whether positive, negative, or neutral²¹⁾. Sentiment analysis is the process of extracting subjective information from text. This is an important area in machine learning and natural language processing^{22,23)}. Machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence that allows systems to automatically learn and improve from experience without explicit programming²⁴⁾. It focuses on developing algorithms and techniques that enable computers to learn from data, recognize patterns, and make predictions^{25,26)}.

On that basis, this study intends to analyze public sentiment toward this policy in Indonesia using data from the X platform. The objective of this study is also to evaluate the performance of the aforementioned machine learning algorithms in classifying these sentiments. The novelty lies in the integration of social media-based sentiment analysis with machine learning techniques. This not only offers a deeper understanding of public responses but also bridges the use of digital technologies in environmental policy analysis in Indonesia.

The outline of this study begins with the background and

research objectives of sentiment analysis concerning the prohibition of single-use plastic bags. The next section outlines the methodological framework. The following section explains the results of sentiment analysis and discusses the research findings based on the performance of each algorithm. The final section reveals the conclusions and further recommendations.

2. Methodology

This section details the procedures and tools for analyzing public sentiment toward the single-use plastic ban policy in Indonesia. In general, the methodological framework in this study consisted of data collection, pre-processing (cleaning and transforming), labeling, modeling, and analysis, as shown in Figure 2. Data collection employed Tweet Harvest v2.6.1 software, whereas the other subsequent processes utilized RapidMiner software due to its powerful data analysis and machine learning modeling tools^{27,28)}.

2.1. Sample size determination

Two approaches were used to preliminarily determine the sample, depending on the type of population. The chosen population was the total Indonesian population in 2024 (larger population) and the number of Indonesian people using the X platform until 2024 (smaller population). The confidence levels were tested at 90%, 95%, and 99% because they are commonly used in engineering studies. Cochran's method, as written in Eq. (1) and Eq. (2), was utilized for large populations, whereas Yamane's method, Eq. (3), was utilized for small populations^{29,30)}.

$$n_0 = \frac{z^2 p(1-p)}{\alpha^2} \tag{1}$$

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + (n_0 - 1)N} \tag{2}$$

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(\alpha)^2} \tag{3}$$

where n_0 is the first estimation of sample size, z is the axis value of two-tailed z distribution depending on the confidence level, p is the predicted proportion sample in the population, α is the significance level or margin of error, n is the sample size, and N is the population size.

2.2. Data collection

The X platform was used as the data source to understand people's views on the ban on single-use plastics. Tweet data were limited to X users located in Indonesia or using the Indonesian language. This coverage provided a broad perspective on public sentiment, but might not fully represent the views of individuals who did not use X as their social media platform. Tweets relevant to this topic were collected using the Indonesian keyword "kantong plastik sekali pakai" (meaning "single-use plastic bags") in the period from 2019 to 2023. The code involved in data collection is listed in Table 1.

Fig. 2: Methodological framework

Table 1: Code for data collection

```

#@title X Auth Token
X_auth_token = '5f860e266c147a014f12b3117e00068d6b6946db'
# Import required Python package
!pip install pandas
# Install Node.js (because tweet-harvest built using Node.js)
!sudo apt-get update
!sudo apt-get install -y ca-certificates curl gnupg
!sudo mkdir -p /etc/apt/keyrings
!curl -fsSL https://deb.nodesource.com/gpgkey/nodesource-repo.gpg.key | sudo gpg --
dearmor -o /etc/apt/keyrings/nodesource.gpg
!NODE_MAJOR=20 && echo "deb [signed-by=/etc/apt/keyrings/nodesource.gpg]
https://deb.nodesource.com/node_${NODE_MAJOR}.x nodistro main" | sudo tee
/etc/apt/sources.list.d/nodesource.list
!sudo apt-get update
!sudo apt-get install nodejs -y
# Crawl Data
filename = 'Plastik.csv'
search_keyword = 'Kantong Plastik Sekali Pakai until:2019-01-01 since:2023-12-31
lang:id'
limit = 1500
!npx --yes tweet-harvest@2.6.1 -o "{filename}" -s "{search_keyword}" -l {limit} --
token {X_auth_token}
import pandas as pd
# Specify the path to your CSV file
file_path = f"tweets-data/{filename}"
# Read the CSV file into a pandas DataFrame
df = pd.read_csv(file_path, delimiter=",")
# Display the DataFrame
display(df)
# Check the length of the DataFrame
num_rows = len(df)
print(f"The number of rows in the DataFrame is: {num_rows}")

```

2.3. Data pre-processing

The collected data underwent a series of pre-processing stages, i.e., data cleaning and transformation.

2.3.1. Data cleaning

Initially, data cleaning was employed to remove special characters, links, and irrelevant elements. Afterward, case folding was conducted to convert all the letters in the text to lowercase letters for a more consistent analysis. Tokenization was also performed to divide the text into individual words and to apply the filtering process to remove words that did not make a significant contribution to sentiment analysis. The RapidMiner operators used for data cleaning are given in Figure 3.

2.3.2. Data transformation

The process document from the data operator generates word vectors from string attributes using the term frequency-inverse document frequency ($TF - IDF$), which indicates the importance of a word in a particular document³¹. TF , calculated based on Eq. (4), refers to how often a word appears in a document compared to the total number of words used in the document. This parameter considers all words in a document to be equally important³².

On the other side, IDF enhances the number of unique words present in the document and decreases the value of commonly used terms. It is used to measure the importance of how many times a term or word appears³³. The calculation follows Eq. (5).

$$TF = T/D \quad (4)$$

$$IDF(T) = N/D \quad (5)$$

where T states how many times a term or word appears, D is the number of words in the document, and N is the total number of words.

Zero cannot be in the denominator, hence, adding 1 to it avoids division by zero, resulting in Eq. (6). The final formula in Eq. (7) was applied to measure the importance of a word in a collection of documents.

$$IDF = \frac{\log N}{DF+1} \quad (6)$$

$$TF - IDF = TF \times \frac{\log N}{DF+1} \quad (7)$$

where DF is the number of occurrences of term T in the document.

The document processing operator from the data performs several processes to prepare the dataset for use in developing models for sentiment analysis. The processes applied to the dataset were tokenize, transform cases, filter stopwords, and filter tokens by length. The tokenization divides tweets into sequences of tokens and terms. It also removes punctuation and white spaces from the tweets³⁴.

The transformation case converts all uppercase letters to lowercase letters and vice versa. The researcher chose to change to lowercase in the parameters section³⁵.

The connecting words in tweets were removed using the Indonesian StopWords Filter Operator. Words such as is, then, so, then, although, only, a, but, that, although, namely, that is, which, and others, were also eliminated³¹. Filter tokens by length explore all tokenized terms and filter out words that are shorter or longer than a specified number of characters. Researchers used a minimum of 4 and a maximum of 25 characters per word. The RapidMiner operators used for data transformation are schemed in Figure 4.

2.4. Data labeling

In order to train a machine learning algorithm, tweet data should be manually labeled with sentiments, as outlined in Table 2. This means that each tweet is labeled as positive, negative, or neutral according to the expression of the sentiment contained within it. Consequently, it is important to develop models that can automatically classify sentiments³⁶.

2.5. Data Modeling: Training and testing

Three machine learning algorithms were applied, i.e., Naïve Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Decision Tree. The Naïve Bayes algorithm has been widely used for sentiment classification due to its computational efficiency and reliable performance on short-text data, including tweets³⁷. KNN and Decision Tree are also favored in practical sentiment analysis studies because of their ease of implementation and interpretability, particularly when computational resources are limited^{38,39}. In summary, these algorithms have merits in terms of transparency, interpretability, and suitability to the nature and size of the data set, especially in the context of resource-efficient processing using RapidMiner⁴⁰.

Besides, the k-fold cross-validation was not used because this study focused on evaluating model performance using holdout validation at various data split ratios. Although k-fold cross-validation offers more robust performance estimates, the holdout validation approach is more suitable for comparative analysis of different training-test proportions. Furthermore, holdout validation is superior in providing prompt estimation with minimal computational cost⁴¹.

The dataset was divided into training and testing data with different ratios of 60:40, 70:30, and 80:20. The training data were used to train the algorithm model, whereas test data were used to test the model's performance. This data sharing aided in evaluating the model's ability to predict sentiments with varying accuracy. The RapidMiner operators used in the modeling process are revealed in Figure 5.

Fig. 3: RapidMiner’s operators used for data cleaning

Fig. 4: RapidMiner’s operators used for data transformation

Table 2: Data labeling

Text	Sentiment
Come on, everyone, stop using single-use plastic. If you go to minimarkets or stalls, bring your own shopping bag, and bring a Tumblr instead of buying bottled water.	Positive
It’s true, I only use it once at home, I even use it to store all sorts of things, the small ones are usually for storing chili sauce or fried onions, and the big ones are usually for storing vegetables or even for storing plastic bags like this.	Negative
When they arrived in front of the main gate, several temple volunteer officers asked residents who were dressed in traditional clothing to hand over plastic bags and disposable plastic bags for the offerings they brought.	Neutral

Fig. 5: RapidMiner’s operators used for data modeling

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Results of sample size adequacy test

Figure 6 demonstrates the trends that reflect fluctuations in

online conversations regarding environmental regulation. From a total of 1190 tweets, this cleaning process resulted in 1038 tweets. The first term of 2019 recorded the highest peak with 390 tweets, which then decreased to 237 tweets in the first term of 2020. The highest peak occurred in the

second term of 2020, with 466 tweets, reflecting a significant response to this issue in Indonesian society. However, conversations drastically decreased in the first and second halves of 2021, with 74 and 18 tweets, respectively. Although there was a positive alteration in the first and second terms of 2022, with 95 and 100 tweets in a successive term, it is still below the peak in 2020. The first and second terms of 2023 recorded 64 and 95 tweets, successively, indicating that the ban on single-use plastics in Indonesia remains problematic. Attention, even though the intensity of the conversation did not reach peak levels. The Indonesian population in 2024 is recorded at 279,298,049⁴²⁾, while the number of Indonesian people who used X as their active social media is 24.69 million⁴³⁾.

The sample size determination for both large and small populations using Cochran’s method and Yamane’s method is 68-100 for a confidence interval of 90%, 385-400 for a confidence interval of 95%, and 10,000-13,507 for a confidence interval of 99%, as served in Table 3.

The implication is that a sample size of 1038 tweets can represent the entire X users in Indonesia. In other words, it still complies with a meaningful statistical basis at a confidence level of 96.5% (margin of error of 3.5%). In the context of social media, where active users are more likely to engage in public policy discussions, this sample offers valuable insights into the opinions of this influential group⁴⁴⁾. This approach also increases the possibility of capturing public opinion across a broad spectrum⁴⁵⁾.

Fig. 6: Frequency of tweets from 2019-2023

Table 3: Results of sample size determination

Parameter	Confidence Level 90%	Confidence Level 95%	Confidence Level 99%
z , two-tailed	-1.64	-1.96	-2.33
p	0.5	0.5	0.5
α	0.10	0.05	0.01
n_0	68	385	13,515
N_1 , Indonesian Population (Larger Population)	279,798,049	279,798,049	279,798,049
N_2 , Indonesian X Platform Users (Smaller Population)	24,690,000	24,690,000	24,690,000
n_1 , Cochran’s Method	68	385	13,514
n_2 , Cochran’s Method	68	385	13,507
n_1 , Yamane’s Method	100	400	10,000
n_2 , Yamane’s Method	100	400	10,000

3.2. Performance of Naïve Bayes, KNN, and Decision Tree algorithms

Naïve Bayes is a machine learning algorithm based on Bayes’ theorem. This algorithm assumes independence between the predictor variables. This simplicity and independence assumption make Naïve Bayes fast and efficient in classifying data on a large scale. Naïve Bayes

is suitable for text classification and simple pattern recognition⁴⁶⁾.

Sentiment classification is carried out by calculating the posterior probabilities $P(C|X)$, where C is the sentiment class (positive, negative, or neutral), and X represents the set of features (words or phrases). The independence assumption among features significantly reduces the computational complexity and enhances the efficiency. In

this study, the multinomial Naïve Bayes variant was employed, as it is well suited for discrete features such as word frequencies.

KNN is a machine learning algorithm that classifies objects based on the nearest-neighbor data in a vector space. It does not use any model to match the new data with the training set. In contrast, KNN is based only on the distance from the test data to the training data and is suitable for nonlinear cases and when the data distribution is unknown⁴⁷⁾.

Other than that, Decision Tree is a machine learning algorithm that models problem solutions into a tree structure and divides data into nodes based on their attributes. It is easy to interpret and does not require a complex data preparation process. This algorithm is frequently used for data classification and prediction⁴⁸⁾.

Based on the machine learning algorithm performance data provided, Naïve Bayes showed the most optimal results among the three algorithms, as summarized in Table 4. Naïve Bayes was able to consistently increase its prediction accuracy from 85.63% at a train-to-test data ratio of 60:40 to 87.99% at a ratio of 70:30 and reached the highest accuracy of 89.73% when the training-data ratio was altered to 80:20.

Table 4: Model performance under several holdout variations

Algorithm Models	60:40 Ratio	70:30 Ratio	80:20 Ratio
Naïve Bayes	85.63%	87.99%	89.73%
KNN	68.38%	79.16%	78.95%
Decision Tree	76.28%	78.95%	79.26%

The increasing amount of training data by Naïve Bayes indicates that the algorithm does not experience overfitting. Naïve Bayes' ability to model the probability of correlation between predictor variables and target variables also makes it suitable for data classification⁴⁹⁾. Meanwhile, the performance of KNN becomes poor when the training data ratio escalates from 70:30 to 80:20, where the accuracy alleviates from 79.16% to 78.95%. This implies that KNN starts to experience overfitting because it adjusts too much to noise and outliers in the increasingly large training data. KNN's high dependency on numerical data also influences its performance less than optimal for classification⁴⁷⁾.

For sentiment classification, a new tweet is determined based on the majority class among the 'k' closest labeled tweets, using distance metrics such as the Euclidean distance in vector space. This study used $k = 5$ as the default, and *TF-IDF* features to calculate distances. Unlike Naïve Bayes, KNN does not involve an explicit training phase, making it computationally expensive during inference and prone to overfitting when dealing with noisy social media data.

The decision tree algorithm is in the middle position between Naïve Bayes and KNN in terms of prediction accuracy. This algorithm constructs a tree structure in

which nodes represent features, branches represent decision rules, and leaves represent sentiment classes. The tree recursively splits the dataset based on the feature values that yield the highest information gain. In RapidMiner, the Gini index is used as the splitting criterion²¹⁾. Decision Trees are interpretable and provide a visual understanding of how certain keywords influence sentiment classification, but they are prone to overfitting unless pruned properly^{26,50)}. Although the decision tree accuracy continues to signify as the training data increases, its value is still below that of Naïve Bayes for all ratio comparisons. The limited complexity of the decision tree model is a factor in its performance, which does not surpass Naïve Bayes.

3.3. The Naïve Bayes as the best algorithm

The Naïve Bayes algorithm is a classification method based on Bayes' theorem with the assumption of "purity" or "simplicity" (naïve) of the relationship between the features used in classification⁵¹⁾. This algorithm is often used in text analysis, pattern recognition, and other data classifications. There are several steps in the Naïve Bayes algorithm calculation process and formula, i.e., training data, class probabilities, feature probabilities, posterior probability, and classification^{49,50)}.

The training data were used to train the Naïve Bayes model. This data must contain samples that have been labeled (for example, data that has been labeled as "positive" or "negative" or "neutral"). The probability of each class appearing in the training data is calculated. This was performed by counting the number of times each class appeared in the training data and dividing it by the total amount of training data.

$$P(C) = \frac{\text{Number of samples with a certain class}}{\text{Total number of samples in the training data}}$$

The probability of occurrence of each feature in each class was calculated. This involves counting the number of times a particular feature appeared in each class.

$$P(X_i|C) = \frac{\text{Number of samples with a particular feature in a particular class}}{\text{Number of samples with a certain class}}$$

After calculating the class and feature probabilities within each class, the posterior probability for each class was calculated using the input data (features).

$$P(C|X) = \frac{P(C) \cdot P(X_1|C) \cdot P(X_2|C) \cdot \dots \cdot P(X_n|C)}{P(X)}$$

where X is the input feature vector (e.g. a classified text document).

The class with the highest posterior probability is selected as the class generated by the Naïve Bayes model. The Naïve Bayes algorithm is simple and efficient but has a

fairly strong assumption that all features in the input data are independent of each other, which is often not met in the real world ³⁷). Nevertheless, this algorithm often provides good results in many cases, particularly in text classification, such as sentiment analysis.

Based on the three confusion matrix tables provided in Table 5, the overall performance of Naïve Bayes improves with an increasing proportion of training data. This is reflected in the overall accuracy, which continued to

intensify from 85.63% (60:40 ratio) to 89.73% (80:20 ratio). Specifically, the increase in Naïve Bayes performance is also marked by improvements in the precision and recall values for almost all classes. For example, the precision and recall of the positive class continue to enhance as the amount of training data increases. The positive precision changed from 90.06% to 92.75% and 95.98%, while the positive recall signified from 90.98% to 91.27% and 90.39%, respectively.

Table 5: Confusion matrix for the Naïve Bayes algorithm

	Negative	Positive	Neutral	Class Recall
60:40 Ratio				
Actual Negative	625	36	26	90.98%
Actual Positive	42	143	6	74.87%
Actual Neutral	27	3	66	68.75%
Class Precision	90.06%	78.57%	67.35%	
70:30 Ratio				
Actual Negative	627	36	24	91.27%
Actual Positive	29	156	6	81.68%
Actual Neutral	20	2	74	77.08%
Class Precision	92.75%	80.41%	71.15%	
80:20 Ratio				
Actual Negative	168	17	6	87.96%
Actual Positive	36	621	30	90.39%
Actual Neutral	2	9	85	88.54%
Class Precision	81.55%	95.98%	70.25%	

The same phenomenon also occurs in the negative and neutral classes, although it does not always consistently increase. For example, the negative recall value decreased slightly from 81.68% (70:30) to 87.96% (80:20), although it was still better than 74.87% (60:40). This trend reflects that the Naïve Bayes model can utilize increasing training data to improve its prediction ability without overfitting. However, the performance in minority classes, such as neutral, is still not optimal, and there is still room for further improvement.

Most X users appreciated the policy of banning single-use plastics, as seen by 70.6% of their positive opinions. This indicates a high level of environmental awareness. Nevertheless, the government needs to pay attention to 19.6% of negative opinions. This can be affected by industrial and business players. Socialization and discussion are needed to reduce this negative opinion. In addition, 9.8% of the neutral opinions still needed to be

converted to support the policy. Massive education and information are important to increase community support. The frequencies of the words and their associated classifications are tabulated in Table 6. In the meantime, Figure 7 illustrates the visual representation of word clouds for positive, neutral, and negative classifications. The word cloud visually represents the words employed within the dataset. Words that are used more frequently are displayed in a larger size within the word cloud.

Overall, it can be concluded that Naïve Bayes shows a positive performance and responds well to increasing the amount of training data. This makes Naïve Bayes worth considering for application to similar classification cases in the future. High community support is an important asset for implementing a single-use plastic ban policy in the future ⁵²). However, efforts to increase support from the government should be continued through outreach and education to change negative and neutral opinions.

Table 6: Word count per sentiment

Positive		Negative		Neutral	
Word	Count	Word	Count	Word	Count
plastik (plastic)	251	plastik (plastic)	44	plastik (plastic)	24
kantong (bag)	182	kantong (bag)	38	kantong (bag)	18
pakai (use)	169	pakai (use)	33	pakai (use)	18
penggunaan (utilize)	64	sampah (trash)	9	penggunaan (utilize)	8
sampah (trash)	52	belanja (shop)	6	bebas (free)	4
belanja (shop)	36	kertas (paper)	6	belanja (shop)	3
mengurangi (reduce)	35	bahan (material)	5	Indonesia	3
lingkungan (environment)	29	galon (gallon)	5	Jakarta	3
pasar (market)	23	penggunaan (utilize)	5	larang (ban)	3
bawa (carry)	20	kain (fabric)	4	larangan (prohibition)	3
galon (gallon)	19	ulang (recycle)	4	ramah (friendly)	3
botol (bottle)	17	botol (bottle)	3	daerah (region)	2
kemasan (packaging)	15	diciptakan (created)	3	lingkungan (environment)	2
masyarakat (community)	14	dipakai (used)	3	LLHPB*	2
bebas (free)	13	dipake (used)	3	tingkat (level)	2

* Lembaga Lingkungan Hidup dan Penanggulangan Bencana (Environment and Disaster Management Unit)

Fig. 7: Wordcloud: Positive (a), Negative (b), Neutral (c)

4. Conclusions

This study analyzes public sentiment on the X Platform regarding the policy of single-use plastic ban in Indonesia by utilizing machine learning algorithms. The Naïve Bayes algorithm is proven to be the most effective, with the highest accuracy of 89.73% at 80:20 ratio. This algorithm can improve its performance as the amount of training data increases without overfitting. The results of the analysis show that the majority of the public has a positive attitude (70.6%), supporting this policy. Only 19.6% have a negative attitude and 9.8% have a neutral attitude.

The results of this study can be used as an effort to gain public support for environmental policies. This allows for a faster and more accurate understanding of the dynamics of public opinion, which is valuable for policymakers in formulating and implementing effective and supportive plastic waste management strategies. There needs to be socialization and discussion to reduce negative opinions from several groups. In addition, neutral opinions must be changed to support policies through massive education and information. Thus, the government can formulate effective

and environmentally friendly policies that are supported by the majority of the community.

Future analysis can be realized by combining data from various social media platforms, conducting offline surveys or direct interviews, and creating additional machine learning algorithms to better understand the Indonesian language and cultural context. Several options, such as Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), can be further incorporated to validate the current findings due to higher predictive power. The k-fold cross-validation method will also be utilized to improve model robustness.

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Collection, Simulation, Formal analysis, Validation, Visualization. **SS:** Writing—review and editing, Formal analysis, Validation, Visualization, Critical revising. **RYHS, MM, GO, MLDW, NSL, ABA, MS, VL, AY, DD, AAS:** Formal analysis, Validation **AARS, ESAS:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Writing—review and editing.

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